

Display Report

Analysis Info

Analysis Name D:\Data\Gosia\2023\M. Sulik\23.06.20\MJ-III-023_23.06.20_3.d
Method Tune_pos_Mid.m
Sample Name MJ-III-023 Instrument impact HD 1819696.00156
Comment

Acquisition Parameter

Source Type	ESI	Ion Polarity	Positive	Set Nebulizer	0.3 Bar
Focus	Active	Set Capillary	3600 V	Set Dry Heater	200 °C
Scan Begin	400 m/z	Set End Plate Offset	-500 V	Set Dry Gas	4.0 l/min
Scan End	1350 m/z	Set Charging Voltage	2000 V	Set Divert Valve	Source
		Set Corona	0 nA	Set APCI Heater	0 °C

